

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ADEDEJI****FIRST NAME: ADEWUNMI****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****(PHD) COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

5 key concepts

1. Writing a Good Academic Essay (EUCLID 2024, 10)
2. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 25)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 41-42)
5. Paraphrases (EUCLID 2024, 37-37)

INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing essays has become an indispensable yardstick for presenting and preserving ideas, espousing and sustaining new knowledge, and contributing to existing knowledge through research. For the purpose of this course, the focus will fundamentally be primarily on academic writing for scholarly purposes.

Academic writing is solely empirical research findings by scholars, which could be in the form of a manuscript or published in newspapers, journals, or other periodicals. It seeks to provide answers to hypotheses and communicate ideas based on evidence. For the purpose of this response paper, I shall be commenting on the above-mentioned concepts learned from the course pack ACA-401D and the basic tutorial video, Euclid University.

2) WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

Chapter one of the course pack discusses the rudiments of writing a good academic essay. To write a good academic essay, some rule of thumb has to be followed. The chapter

elaborated on writing a good essay from the introduction to the body and conclusion. The introduction part of the essay will start from general to specific, where you introduce the topic areas, answer the question with a thesis statement, and provide a summary of the essay. The body consists of the essay paragraphs, each as a building block in constructing your argument by developing discussion, displaying your grasp of materials you read and presenting exposition and evidence to develop your argument, using relevant examples. The conclusion of the essay takes you to re-stating and re-summarizing the main points and including the final broad statement about the possible implications and future direction for research to qualify the conclusion. (EUCLID 2024, 10). However, this treatise on writing a good essay has reinforced the fact that no essay comes out good without following the above order. I will attempt to always follow this path in pursuing my academic program at EUCLID.

3) PLAGIARISM

Simply put, plagiarism connotes when a writer uses someone else's work without referencing the writer. It could be from a text, manuscript, journal, or the internet, and not give credit to the original writer. In academia, using a source and not referencing it is a serious offense. This attracts serious consequences. However, while it is not an academic offence to use another author's work, it is apposite to always give credit to such author to denote the original source of the work. This way, one will not be guilty of plagiarism. Bearing the gravity of the offense of plagiarism in mind, the importance of giving credit to the original author of information cannot be overemphasized. Therefore, I will always be mindful of plagiarism throughout my program at EUCLID.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

American and British English are both variants of world English, and as such, they are more similar than different, especially with the "educated" or "scientific" English. It has been established that the differences range from pronunciation, spelling, same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation, same words but different or additional meanings. This stems from their national histories and cultural development (EUCLID 2024, 25).

However, to prevent ambiguity, it is apposite to stick with the version the student is conversant with throughout the academic writing. Naturally, being from Nigeria, a former British colony, I have always used the British English version and will adhere to it till the end of my academic pursuit in EUCLID.

5) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide connotes documenting as a writer using his perspectives and some writing styles or regular approaches. It is a manual that spells out the style of a particular

writer. It is generally connected to different types of writing. Such writing could be technical, business, or commercial writing, journalism, and web copywriting emphasizing consistency. It is published as a collaborative effort so that every writer will have the opportunity to contribute and not reflect just a writer's writing style. However, the emphasis is to provide consistency and coherence in writing. It is like a reservoir of knowledge that writers can tap into when writing, using various documented style guides. The fact that there is no single authoritative source for writing English simply means that the debate on style will keep evolving (EUCLID 2024, 41 & 42).

It is very instructive to note that while style in writing English is subject to the writer's perspective, it must be coherent and consistent. This will be invaluable to me during my degree, as I will always utilize this in all my papers.

6) PARAPHRASES

Paraphrases are another style of referencing another writer's work by producing it in your own words. It is generally accepted in academia that having too many paraphrases in a write-up does not make the papers look good; thus, the need to use paraphrases cannot be overemphasized. However, when you use paraphrases, it is on the premise that it is written differently from the source but simultaneously conveys the same message. The paraphrases must differ from the original author's language and style, accurately represent what the original author wrote, and the source of information must be quoted.

This treatise on the use of paraphrases is very germane and instructive, considering its importance in writing a good academic essay. It will go a long way in helping me in my academic pursuit in EUCLID. It will be one of my watchwords.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth edition. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.